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CUSTOMER SATISFACTION, REPURCHASE INTENTION AND DEALER LOYALTY IN COMMERCIAL
VEHICLE TYRE PURCHASE

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ABSTRACT

Many organizations realize that it costs less to keep a customer than to attract a new one. In an era of decreasing population growth, there are simply not enough new customers to satisfy the demands for growth required by firms interested in long-term shareholder value. One alternative is to enlarge market share by cutting price. Another approach is by expensive promotional campaigns or product line extensions. A more profitable approach may be to develop strategies that focus on achieving customer loyalty, both among existing customers and in new markets. The rationale for investigating the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is that satisfaction with a product or a service affects buying intentions as well as actual future behaviour in a positive way. This study aims at providing more insight into the relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty. It might be expected that satisfaction with a dealer, next to satisfaction with the tyre itself, could have an effect on dealer loyalty and brand loyalty. The study especially stresses the interaction between dealer and customer. The aim is to attempt to measure the strength and the direction of these inter-relationships. Customer satisfaction is the end result of almost all aspects of value added. After all, the benefits of higher product quality, lower costs, better inventory management, and improved logistics should all be passed on to the end customer. Anywhere a supplier can add to its services, either by advice or 'hands-on' activities is a potential improvement in customer satisfaction. And customer satisfaction translates directly into increased business.

Key words: customer satisfaction, dealer loyalty, replacement buyer, tyre, Commercial vehicles.

Introduction

Store image has been recognised as an important antecedent of store satisfaction and loyalty. In fact, Martineau (1958) explains that if individuals have a favourable image of the store, they will most probably develop a certain degree of loyalty corresponding to the favourableness of the image. Customer satisfaction or service quality has been demonstrated to affect or drive store loyalty (such as positive word-of-mouth, repurchase intention) across a range consumer products. A review of the relevant literatures suggests that the loyalty concept could be conceptualized as a two-dimensional construct (i.e. loyalty is made up of attitude and behaviour). Another thought is that it is probably better seen as attitude than behaviour and, finally, loyalty is closer to a behavioural intention than an attitude. The firm's marketing success largely depends on the dealers, because these persons are the ones who have the most direct influence on the customers. In this sense, estimating customers judgment about their buying experience and evaluating the aspects that influence their perception of this service most, could help making the product a success. Any business can succeed with a help of customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction can be defined as the overall evaluation of the purchase and consumption experience, which focuses on perceived product or service performance compared with the pre-purchase expectations. Customer satisfaction has become a main objective of all companies and one of the key issues in contemporary marketing literature, related to increased profitability. One of the most important factors affecting satisfaction is service quality. Berry et al. (1988) defined service quality as an attitude of the consumer relating to the results from comparisons between his expectations of service and his perceptions of actual service performance.

Satisfaction and Store Loyalty

Organizations world-wide are using teams to improve the quality of their products and services and recognize that this teamwork should include suppliers. Companies are to establish supply chain partnerships so that suppliers are motivated and able to provide the materials needed to meet customer expectations. Cooper & Gardner (1993) understand that their performance depends very much on the performance of their suppliers. They are not competing with their competitors by themselves, but rather, by their whole supply chains. Therefore, partnering with suppliers has been advocated as a means to obtain best performance from a supply chain.

Ellram, & Edis (1996) described the concept of partnering as the creation of cooperative business alliances between constituencies within an organisation and between an organisation and its suppliers and customers. Many authors point out the importance of the partnering efforts among the supply chain partners. Kanji and Wong (1998) share the view that the creation and enhancement of the customer-supplier partnership is a major quality practice prescribed as an indispensable part of an organizations total quality system. There are some obvious ways that suppliers can help improve end users customer satisfaction. Genna (1997) points out that steps to improve supplier product quality, such as defect-free and on-time shipments, often can carry through to help provide the same quality to end users.

Review of the Literature

There are number of studies of store loyalty and the inter-relationship between brand loyalty and store loyalty. Bloemer et al (1990) in general, store loyalty is an intervening variable between satisfaction with the product/service and brand loyalty. Store image has been recognised as an important antecedent of store satisfaction and loyalty. In fact, Martineau (1958) explains that if an individual have a favourable image of the store, they will most probably develop a certain degree of loyalty corresponding to the favourableness of the image. Customer satisfaction or service quality has been demonstrated to affect or drive store loyalty such as positive word-of-mouth, repurchase intention across a range of consumer products. The key to success lies not only in having a good product, but also in being able to provide the customer with the level of service they desire. Saraswathi, S. (2008) concluded in the study that customer service is defined as "a function of how well an organization meets the needs of its customers". Post-sales service is a concern area for customers as their expectations on the over all quality continue to go higher. Moreover, the increasingly growing demand for after sales support and better services has compelled the manufacturers to focus and invest more on R & D, reaching the customer, and satisfaction.

Swan and Oliver (1989) studied the general influence of satisfaction and equity extended to the product sold by the retailer (a new automobile) as well as to the dealership and salesperson. Retailers cannot directly control WOM, an important influence on prospective customers. However, by seeking customer complaints, it may be possible to turn dissatisfied customers into contented buyers and gain positive WOM. Davis (2002) when making a tyre purchase, price was the most important decision criterion (59 percent of respondents) followed by brand name (47 percent of respondents). Seventy-five percent of consumers said they usually buy brands on sale, have coupons, or buy because some kind of special offer is being made. In addition, only 11 percent of consumers said they chose a store due to advertising. A particularly noteworthy finding was that 36 percent of respondents said the tyre dealer's recommendation swayed their decision, indicating the important role in-store representatives may have on consumers tyre purchase decisions.

A study by Mintel (1990) Most customers use more than one distributor for the supply of replacement tyres. Less than 25 percent of respondents said that they used only one distributor whilst over 50 percent said that they used three or more distributors. The main reason for using more than one distributor is for geographical coverage, either in terms of choosing distributor with nearest outlet to each particular location or the need for national coverage followed by to maintain a competitive level of price and service. Factors importance in the choice of dealer is availability of other facilities followed by quality of product and price of product. Safety of the product and durability of the product are the most important factor followed by price of the product. The result found by Bloemer and Lemmink (1992) With respect to dealer loyalty there is a significant partial correlation with the satisfaction with the sales service and the satisfaction with the after-sales service. This means that there is a clear relationship between satisfactions with the sales service. Consumer satisfaction plays an important role in explaining brand and dealer loyalty, 80 percent of the respondents given reason for brand or dealer loyalty were

related to satisfaction. Only 20 percent of the reasons concerned price and other reasons. Satisfaction with the service is an important determinant of dealer loyalty. However, satisfaction with the after-sales service seems to be even more important than satisfaction with sales service.

Statement of the Problem

Commercial Vehicles (CVs) segment covers buses and trucks classified as Medium and Heavy Commercial Vehicles (M & HCVs) and Van, station wagons and smaller weight vehicles, characterized a Light Commercial Vehicles (LCVs). The demand of tyres flows from three segments – Original Equipment (OE), Replacements and Exports. Of the three, the replacement market is the primary source of demand, followed by the OE segment and exports. The study's problems are formulated according to the following objectives.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To identify the major Reasons to buy tyre from different dealer
2. To examine the priority factors for selecting the dealer of choice during the purchase of tyre.

Hypotheses of the Study

- H1: Respondents intensity level is not similar towards reasons for choosing the dealer
 H2: Various reasons do not influence on choice of dealer.

Area of Research and Sampling Procedure

The study aims at analyse how buyer of replacement tyre prefer to buy from dealers and what are the factors are influence the consumers in replacement of tyres in commercial vehicles segments. The researcher collected data in various cities in Tamilnadu. Here totally 485 consumers are considered for the present study after rejecting unfit response. The selection of study area is based on multi stage random sampling technique. But, the selections of sample respondents are based on convenient sampling technique.

Collection of Data

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a structured questionnaire administered in person from the consumer regarding their opinion about their satisfaction on the product. The respondents of this study are owners of the Light and Heavy commercial vehicles who have replaced their product after using the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM). The researcher collected secondary data on sales trends, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the replacement action. This information have been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

Statistical Tools Used

Responses are coded and data entered and then analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 15.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis is used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories. Friedman's comparison test is used to group the variables by comparing mean rank. Stepwise multiple regression analysis is used to measure the linear association between the dependent and independent variables.

Table – 1 Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Frequency	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Age of Respondent	Less than 30 years	30	6.2
	31-40 years	97	20.0
	41-50 years	207	42.7
	51 years & above	151	31.1
Qualification	Primary	215	44.3

Experience	Graduate	122	25.2
	PG/Professional	68	14.0
	Diploma	80	16.5
Type of vehicles owned	Less than 5 years	76	15.7
	5-10 years	165	34.0
	11-15 years	91	18.8
	16-20 years	153	31.5
No. of LCV owned	LCV	281	57.9
	HCV	204	42.1
No. of HCV owned	LCV – 1	207	42.7
	LCV – 2	36	7.4
	LCV 3-5	37	7.6
	LCV more than 5	02	0.4
	HCV – 1	44	9.1
Purchase from more dealer	HCV – 2	96	19.8
	HCV 3-5	48	9.9
	HCV more than 5	16	3.3
	Yes	247	50.9
Reason to buy	No	238	49.1
	Performance	401	82.7
	Preference	84	17.3

Source: Primary Data – computed

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondent considered for the research. Total respondent considered for the research is 485.

Table – 2 Reasons for Purchasing Tyres from Different Dealers

Reasons	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Geographical coverage of outlet	229	92.7
Competitive level of Pricing	20	0.04
Availability	247	100
Continuity of Supply	234	94.7

Source: Primary Data – computed

Respondents are asked the reason for purchasing tyres from more dealers. The results are displayed in the table – 4.2. Among the respondent 247 respondents (100%) have expressed that the availability is one of the major reason for purchasing from more dealer, followed by continuity of supply (94.7%) and geographical coverage (92.7%).

Table – 3 Respondents' Priorities in the Choice of Dealer

Priorities in the choice of dealer	Friedman's test Mean Rank value	Chi-Square Value	P-value	Multiple comparison test
Competitive level of pricing	6.36	2026.355	0.001*	1
Range of product availability	5.56			2
Quality of service	3.48			3,4,5,6,7
Availability of various brands	3.20			
Geographical coverage of outlet	3.16			
Credit facilities	3.13			
Claim settlement	3.05			

Source: Primary Data – computed

Respondents purchase tyres from one or more dealer at the time of replacement, in order to assess the perception of the customer with respect to the various reasons for their preference for buying from more dealers, the respondents are asked to rate the various reasons on selecting the dealer. The respondents' opinions relates to reasons are displayed in table – 3.

Ho-1: Respondents intensity level is not similar towards reasons for choosing the dealer

To know the intensity level of the respondents towards the reasons for selecting a particular dealer, Friedman's test is applied. From the test, the mean rank value ranges from 3.05 to 6.36 and chi-square value (2026.355) is found to be significant at one percent level. Hence, the respondent's intensity level is significantly varied relating to various reasons to buy their replacement tyres from more dealers. Thus, the stated hypothesis (Ho-1) is rejected.

To identify the highest contributing factor among the seven reasons for buying tyres from more dealers, Friedman's multiple comparison tests is applied. The test results grouped seven statements into four different categories. Among the various reasons, competitive level of pricing is the most preferred reason followed by range of product availability. Quality of service, availability of various brands, geographical coverage of outlet, credit facilities and claim settlement are the least preferred choice while choosing the dealer.

Table – 4 Factors Influencing in the Choice of Dealer

R – Value	R Square value	Adjusted R Square value	f – Value	p – Value
0.361	0.30	0.118	10.194	0.001*

Factors	B value	Std. Error	Beta	t – Value	p – Value
(Constant)	4.954	0.289	-	17.132	0.001*
Competitive level of pricing	0.254	0.058	0.190	4.361	0.001*
Range of product availability	0.010	0.256	0.005	0.039	0.969(NS)
Quality of service	0.273	0.279	0.147	0.977	0.329(NS)
Availability of various brands	-0.081	0.189	-0.043	-0.427	0.669(NS)
Geographical coverage of outlet	-0.270	0.072	-0.199	-3.767	0.001*
Credit facilities	-0.083	0.036	-0.102	-2.332	0.020**
Claim settlement	-0.0243	0.096	-0.156	-2.536	0.012**

Source: Primary Data – computed (*significant at one percent, level ** significant at five percent level, NS-Not significant)

The consumer purchases the replacement tyres from different dealers and expects certain benefit in their choice. Table 4 explains the factors influencing the choice of dealer. The factors taken for analysis are effects of competitive level of pricing, range of product availability, quality of service, availability of various brands, geographical coverage of outlet, credit facilities and claim settlement on selection of dealer.

Ho-2: Various reasons do not influence on choice of dealer.

Here, the factors of competitive level of pricing, range of product availability, quality of service, availability of various brands, geographical coverage of outlet, credit facilities and claim settlement are considered as independent variables and choice of dealer is treated as dependent variable. From the f- statistics value (10.194) and p- value (0.001), it is inferred that the independent variables significantly influence on choice of dealer. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. Further, stepwise multiple regressions is applied to identify the most predicted reason in

the choice of dealer. Among the influencing factors, competitive levels of pricing, geographical coverage of outlet are the factors highly influenced while selecting the dealer.

FINDINGS

Most of the respondents are purchasing tyres from different dealers for various reasons. The priority for choosing replacement tyres from more dealers is competitive level of pricing followed by the range of product availability. It is found that respondent's priority in the choice of dealer significantly varied within the group. Where, competitive level of pricing has positive impact on choice of dealer. But, geographical coverage of outlet, credit facilities, and claim settlement has negative impact on choice of dealer. Priority towards choice of dealer is significantly varied towards price, range of product availability, quality of service, availability of various brands and claim settlement factors based on the type of vehicles owned by the respondents.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the buyer buy product form different dealers, among the major reason behind the purchase, competitive level of pricing is the most preferred reason followed by range of product availability. Quality of service, availability of various brands, geographical coverage of outlet, credit facilities and claim settlement are the least preferred choice while choosing the dealer.

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